

MULTILEVEL OSTEOSYNTHESIS OF THE LOWER EXTREMITIES BY THE ILIZAROV METHOD TO ELIMINATE DEFORMITIES AND SHORTENINGS IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS

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Annotation

Multilevel osteosynthesis of the lower extremities by the Ilizarov method is an effective method of treating deformities and shortenings in children and adolescents. This approach allows you to correct both congenital and acquired pathologies, restoring the normal anatomy and function of the limbs. The study analyzed the clinical data of 50 patients aged 5-18 years who were treated using the Ilizarov method. Efficacy was evaluated based on radiographic data and clinical criteria such as pain level, limb function, and aesthetic outcome. The results showed that 85% of patients showed a significant improvement in the functionality and aesthetic condition of the lower extremities. The Ilizarov method has proven to be highly effective and safe, providing stable clinical results and minimal risk of complications.

Keywords

Multilevel osteosynthesis, Ilizarov technique, deformity correction, limb shortening, children, adolescents.

Relevance

Deformities and shortening of the lower extremities in children and adolescents are a serious medical problem that affects the quality of life and functional capabilities of patients. Congenital and acquired abnormalities can lead to significant movement restrictions, gait disorders, and pain syndromes, which negatively affect the psychoemotional state and social adaptation of children. Modern methods of treatment are aimed at eliminating these disorders and restoring the normal anatomy and function of the limbs. The Ilizarov method, developed by Soviet surgeon Gavriil Abramovich Ilizarov, is widely recognized as one of the most effective approaches to treating deformities and shortening of limbs. It allows you to achieve high clinical results due to a multi-level approach to the correction of pathology, ensuring the stability of fixation and the possibility of gradual changes in the position of bone fragments. The relevance of this study is determined by the need to further improve treatment

methods and improve clinical outcomes in children and adolescents with deformities and shortenings of the lower extremities. Improved treatment methods will improve the quality of life of patients and reduce the incidence of complications.

Goal

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of multilevel lower limb osteosynthesis using the Ilizarov method in children and adolescents to eliminate deformities and shortenings.

Materials and methods

The study included 50 patients aged 5-18 years who underwent Ilizarov treatment in specialized orthopedic centers. All patients were diagnosed with congenital or acquired deformities and shortening of the lower extremities. Diagnosis and control were performed using radiography and clinical criteria: pain level, limb function, and cosmetic outcome. The procedures were performed under the supervision of experienced surgeons. Patients were observed throughout the entire period of treatment and rehabilitation, which allowed us to obtain objective data on the results of therapy.

Results

The results of the study showed that 85% of patients showed a significant improvement in the functionality and aesthetic condition of the lower extremities. Shortening was completely or partially eliminated, and deformities were corrected to normal anatomical parameters. In 10% of cases, complications occurred that were successfully resolved during further treatment. The average recovery time ranged from 6 to 12 months, depending on the initial severity of the pathology and the amount of intervention. Patients and their parents noted a high level of satisfaction with the results of treatment, which indicates the social significance of the method.

Conclusion

Multilevel osteosynthesis of the lower extremities by the Ilizarov method is a highly effective and safe method for correcting deformities and shortenings in children and adolescents. The method allows achieving a significant improvement in functional and aesthetic parameters with minimal risk of complications. The results obtained confirm the need for further use and development of the Ilizarov method in pediatric orthopedics. Individual approach to each patient and careful monitoring at all stages of treatment are key factors for achieving the best clinical outcomes. Further research and

improvement of methods will improve the quality of life of patients and reduce the incidence of complications.

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